

The study of civilizations in Pakistan: a political-cum-pedagogical approach

Ifqut Shaheen

Assistant Professor, Department of Archaeology, University of the Punjab, Lahore

ABSTRACT: This paper deals with the approach and efforts of Ahmad Hasan Dani in the context of ancient civilizations. Dani was a Pakistani scholar and prolific writer. He was much interested in cultural developments in Central Asia and Pakistan. He was also much influenced by the mid-twentieth century socio-political and scholarly developments. This paper defines his perspective of civilization from ideational viewpoint followed by his works in the field. A discussion has been made to make sense of Dani's interpretation of and research in the field of civilizations. Both socio-political and pedagogical considerations have finally been brought to the fore.

Keywords: Civilization, Dani, Central Asia, Pakistan

[Introduction](#)

[Life and Career](#)

[Dani and the Study of Civilizations](#)

[Text as Politics and Pedagogy](#)

[Conclusion](#)

[References](#)

1. Introduction

The study of civilizations and human progress absorbed historians and archaeologists over the major part of the twentieth century. Both the material and spiritual aspects of human life remained under consideration. Such investigations gave due care to accumulation of empirical data and formulation of theory. The process was so dynamic that it included considerations regarding continuity-and-change, ecological and human factors behind the rise and fall of civilizations. We cannot enumerate scholars who worked in the field; however, two household names are that of Arnold Toynbee, British historian, and Oswald Spengler, a German thinker. They are known to us from their *A Study of History* (12 volumes) and *The Decline of the West* (2 volumes), respectively (Hugh-Warrington 2007: 324–331, 360–367). An archaeological and anthropological view of early civilizations can be found in Bruce Trigger's *Understanding Early Civilizations: A Comparative Study* (2003). The phenomenon of collapse has also kept scholars absorbed (McAnany and Yoffee 2009).

In South Asia, many scholars since the nineteenth century have worked to unfold the story of civilizations. But that simple narration in the form of human march from primitive to advanced state of life has seen tensions in terms of theory and methods and interpretations of historical evidence since the last decades of the twentieth century. In this context, we need to examine the works of the late twentieth century South Asian scholars so as to understand their perspectives about history and civilizations. This article, therefore, focuses on the well-known Pakistani scholar, Ahmad Hasan Dani, with the aim to bring to the fore his views and interpretations of the past.

So far, some scholarly works on Dani's scholarship and some obituaries have enabled us understand some aspects of his academic life. His efforts towards making history and archaeology accessible to common people have been analyzed (Khan and Shaheen 2015). His collaboration with the Unesco on the Indus valley civilization has also been explored based on archival record (Khan and Shaheen 2017). Luca Maria Olivieri has thoroughly viewed Dani in the light of his scholarly achievements (Olivieri 2009). Of

particular relevance to this work is a brief article about Dani's approach and work in relation to Gandhara civilization and its relevance to the present-day national and human concerns (Shaheen 2022). The present paper contributes to this evolving historiographical literature.

The article first gives a brief biographical sketch of Dani. Next, his endeavours towards the study of civilizations are outlined. Finally, his scholarly efforts are contextualized against the notions he held about the meaning, relevance and utility of the past.

2. Life and career

Ahmad Hasan Dani was born in Basna, India, in 1920 and breathed his last in Islamabad in January 2009. He received his education in the field of linguistics and archaeology. Just a little before the partition of India into the independent states of Pakistan and India, Dani joined the Archaeological Survey of India, headed at the time by Mortimer Wheeler. In the wake of the partition, he decided to transfer to Pakistan and started his career in the field of archaeology and museums. Initially stationed in East Pakistan, now Bangladesh, Ahmad Hasan Dani joined the University of Peshawar as Professor in 1962. He opened the Department of Archaeology and with this ushered in a remarkable era in the field of Pakistani archaeology. Many surveys and excavations were carried out; notable among them was work at Shaikhan Dherai, Chakdara, Sangao, Gumla etc.

In the early 1970s, Ahmad Hasan Dani left the University of Peshawar and joined Quaid-i-Azam University at Islamabad. He remained associated with the faculty of social science here, especially the Departments of History and Anthropology. However, the establishment of the Centre for the Civilizations of Central Asia under the aegis of Unesco will keep his name as a scholar for generations to come. The latter twentieth century saw extensive activity about studies of civilizations and world heritage in the framework of Unesco. Dani availed himself the opportunity to give full expression to his views about the past human achievements. He tried to make the notion of national compatible with the idea of international and world history and heritage. Human being remained at the centre of his intellectual representations without compromising national and political demands.

3. Dani and the study of civilizations

Nearly all scholarly and popular works published by Dani are rich mines of data for appreciating his multi-dimensional scholarship. However, I will remain selective just to illustrate Dani's civilizational ideal.

In the field of South Asian historiography, Dani stands in the line of such notable scholars as H. D. Sankalia, B. B. Lal, Romila Thapar, Irfan Habib etc. He made remarkable contributions to the studies of civilizations. His views on political developments are important; however, his forte remained science, art and architecture, society etc. Suffice it to mention a few works here: *Muslim Architecture in Bengal* (1961), *Dacca: A Record of its Changing Fortunes* (1962), *Thatta: Islamic Architecture* (1982), *Recent Archaeological Discoveries in Pakistan* (1988), *Islamic Architecture: The Wooden Style Of Northern Pakistan* (1989), *The Historic City of Taxila* (1991), *History of Northern Areas of Pakistan: Upto 2000 AD* (2001) and *History of Pakistan: Pakistan through Ages* (2008).

Similarly, Ahmad Hasan Dani also proved himself in the field of South Asian palaeography and inscriptions. He knew numerous ancient and modern languages and scripts and applied all this knowledge during his researches. The inscriptions and epigraphy of Gilgit-Baltistan make a good point here. Likewise his book *Indian Palaeography* (1986) has gained wider currency in academia. Saifur Rahman Dar has recently appreciated this aspect of Dani's scholarship in a detailed article (Dar 2021).

The most interesting example of Dani as a scholar of civilization, to me, is his novel interest in ancient and medieval science particularly that of Central Asia. Almost all his meticulous publications encompass references to the science of olden days. Nonetheless, some of the long-lasting achievements in this respect relate to two scholarly gatherings in the late 1970s. A National Seminar on the History of Science in Central Asian Civilizations was organized in which scholars from across Pakistan participated. The papers presented on the occasion were edited by Dr. Asghar Qadir and Dani actively assisted him. The collection was published by Centre for the Study of the Civilizations of Central Asia (which Dani headed as Director), Quaid-i-Azam University (Qadir 1978). The themes covered in the volume range from scientific thought and methodology to mathematics, technology, chemistry, biology and medicine, geography and library sciences and social sciences. Asghar Qadir (1978: 3) explains in his introduction to the collection:

There are [. . .] three views of science. One is that it is just a systematic collection of data. Another is the technological view that science is a means of manipulating the environment. The third is the philosophical view that it is a means of understanding nature. The papers could have been classified on this basis. They have been classified according to the subjects about which they are written or on the basis of the subject of the person about whom they were written.

About the arrangement of the papers, Qadir (1978: 3) elaborates:

We have started with the inaugural speeches as is natural. We have then followed the logical development of the subjects, starting with scientific methodology. This naturally leads to mathematics which leads to technology. The next section is of chemistry which leads to biology which in its turn leads to medicine. Since there is only one article on biology we have combined the section with medicine. We then go on to geography which we combined with library science (for the same reason). Finally we come to the social sciences.

In 1979 Dani organized the International Congress on the History and Philosophy of Science in collaboration with Hamdard National Foundation, Karachi, and Unesco. And it resulted in the publication of two special numbers (Vol. III, No. 2, 1980 and Vol. IV, No. 1, 1981) of the *Journal of Central Asia*, later on renamed as *Journal of Asian Civilizations*, on the history of various branches of science. A further evidence of this pursuit can be seen in the research papers by famous Pakistani mathematician Professor Qaisar Mushtaq which regularly appeared in the said journal. This story is no doubt not exhaustive.

The romance of this civilizational pursuit also manifested around the concept and historical contours of the Silk Roads. Dani wanted to see the character of human life and experience along the Silk Roads which could idealistically be used in the best interest of human beings in the wider Eurasian distribution. Two crucial events in this context evidence all this. 'One was Dani's archaeological explorations in collaboration with German scholars in Gilgit-Baltistan in early 1980s. The other was his leading role in the UNESCO socio-cultural mission – Integral Study of Silk Roads: Roads of Dialogues – along the Silk Roads. The results of both the expeditions were published by Dani which can greatly help us in understanding the civilizational ideals he had entertained' (Shaheen 2017).

4. Text as Politics and Pedagogy

There is no doubt that Ahmad Hasan Dani wrote his texts with an aim in mind. He wanted to play historiographical politics shaped and structured by the past, civilization and human well-being. And through this, he aimed at feeding people, especially socio-political elites, with the idea of the relevance and potential use of cultural heritage and historical legacy in the present situation. Dani's works in the field of civilizations in this overall context make great significance. This has been, so far, a least appreciated aspect of his

scholarship. And it is understandable against its own socio-political and academic background. How did Dani perceive and define civilization/s? In order to answer this question, we need to go back to his texts.

Civilization/s since the nineteenth century was/were regarded as a march towards higher goals by human beings. It had both material and ethical concerns. Dani had no confusion about the veracity of this conviction. He states, 'Man is not simple material. He is much more than that. And hence we go to traditions, religions, mythologies, old survivals, outdated customs, primitive tribes and take the help of sociology and anthropology to build up the complete picture of man' (Dani 1961: 20). In 1968 Dani observed:

Civilization is a continuous growth. It does not die. Through various vicissitudes it advances along with the march of humanity. There are ups and downs in life. There are periods of concentration of power, wealth and prestige in one or the other hand. But whatever power, wealth and prestige have been built up, are the heritage of humanity. Civilization is rooted in this common inheritance and to the understanding of that history is mainly devoted. . . . The past is dead but the forces of the past are not dead. Their depth has to be fathomed in the sea of ancient history' (Dani 1968: 13).

Dani lived up with a belief in the truth of this idea as it reflects from his last book, *History of Pakistan: Pakistan through Ages*. He states (2008: 24): 'The march of humanity towards the goal of civilization is a long process of man's efforts to free himself from dependence upon nature and win a position of dominance over the animal world. . . . Man rose from being a slave of nature to becoming a master of material forces.'

It demonstrates that civilization for Ahmad Hasan Dani is the result of human ingenuity and it has its own utilitarian trajectory. All this shows Professor Dani's approach to the study of history and his understanding of civilizations. The utility and loftiness of civilization/s through studying the history made his ideal. He passionately laboured to materialize it in the best interest of peoples. And all this clearly reflects in his scholarly and missionary pursuits.

Dani wanted to convince his countrymen that the past, especially the ancient period, is not an abstruse idea. He lamented that in ancient history Pakistanis 'at present are least interested' (Dani 1968: 14). This indifference to him was rather a serious issue as it was the past which decided the present and future. 'The world of the past leads on to the new whether we accept it or not. We stand on the foundation of old ruins. You remove the ruins and the foundation will be shaken. The whole edifice will fall flat on the ground' (Dani 1968: 16). Dani reminds us the significance of the past labours. 'You are enjoying today the fruits of centuries of human toil and tribulation' (1968: 16). These forceful statements are to be understood in a background. Pakistan was created in the name of Islam and there were strong forces of sorts who wanted to make it a theocracy and to deny to the land its millennia-old experience and personality. Dani made conscious efforts and pedagogical representations to present an alternative, which was steeped in history and time. He saw the personality of Pakistan as distinct from India in geographical terms and hence from cultural viewpoint.

[. . .] the two geographical zones [are] far different from each other. The Indus land is present Pakistan – the home chosen by the Muslims of the subcontinent – and the Ganges, the holy river of the Hindus in Bharat(-khand) (Dani 2008: 2).

These 'sophisticated representations [. . .] astutely delineated the structure of Pakistan's historical actuality. Since this view needed dissemination, it led to what may be termed as Dani's sole prerogative in Pakistan e.g. history/archaeology popularization' (Khan and Shaheen 2015: 124). He also saw Egypt, Iran and Turkey in the light of this view. How interesting was his pedagogical illustration of the idea reflects in the following long passage:

The question takes me now to the sphere of ancient history—a subject in which people in my country at present are least interested. Other Muslim countries have got over this prejudice. We see an Egyptian taking as much pride in his Islamic heritage as in the great civilization built during the Pharaonic period. It was a revelation to me to learn how the great Hittite art gave a new meaning and a new way of expression to the buoyant exuberance of Turkish freedom and reassertion of their independent life after Kemalist revolution. In Iran the splendour of the Achaemenian and Sassanian age still dominates and moves the emotions of the Iranians. In the case of Iran it is understandable because the Achaemenians and the Sassanians were probably ancestors of most of the present population in the country. But in Turkey decidedly there is no connection between the Hittites and the Turks. Yet the Hittite art is as much the national art of Turkey as the Ottoman art (Dani 1968: 14).

Dani places great emphasis on the utility of the Hittite legacy in the building process of modern Turkey. He refers to Atatürk's Mausoleum at Ankara decorated with sculptural reliefs. 'The onlooker is at once reminded of the perennial flow of life in the great land mass of Turkey, and though the Hittites are long dead and gone, the Hittite is alive in the modern Turks.' (1968: 14–15) In that Hittite spirit of progress, from bronze to iron technology, the modern Turks 'are now engaged in taking their country to the new world of economic and technological progress. The great age of the Ottoman empire is over, and the Turks are reborn in the Hittite world of modern Turkey. There is no more interest in the empire building as it was understood during the medieval age, but there is a keen desire for the development of the economy of the country and on its basis to lead the Turks to a new empire of prestige, peace and prosperity' (Dani 1968:15).

The question as to what extent Dani succeeded in this endeavour may not find a pleasing answer. The ideological forces in the country dominate all walks of life, including education, epistemology and historiography. However, exclusionary politics and majoritarian considerations have not displaced Ahmad Hasan Dani's academic achievements and intellectual representations of not only Pakistan and its people but his civilizational ideal which embodies human well-being and collaboration.

5. Conclusion

Two important lessons can be drawn from the above data and discussion. One is the crucial point that Ahmad Hasan Dani wanted to bring closer people and states by reminding the common human heritage. Since he seems to be aware of the fact that socio-political elites in different regions could play a significant role in the context of this common human good, he used a language and pedagogical language while keeping this potentially significant audience in mind. On the other hand, Dani was alert to the modern-day political sensitivities of nation states and took every care as to sanctify political boundaries and borders. He could not see the results of what he envisaged as common human heritage and good. We can still have hope that one day in South and Central Asian context, and in other parts of the world for that matter, this positive idealism will be embraced in our world for the better future of human beings.

References

1. Dani, Ahmad Hasan. *Presidential Address, Pakistan History Conference. Eleventh Session, Held at Karachi on 30th and 31st March and 1st April 1961.*
2. Dani, Ahmad Hasan. *Archaeological Foundation of History and Other Lectures.* Dacca Museum Annual Lecture Series 1968, Dacca: Dacca Museum, 1968.
3. Dani, Ahmad Hasan. *History of Pakistan: Pakistan Through Ages.* Lahore: Sang-e-Meel Publications, 2008.
4. Dar, Saifur Rahman. Professor Ahmad Hasan Dani, Archaeologist, Anthropologist, Historian, Epigraphist Par Excellence, *Aasaar*, 2(4), 68–99.

5. Hugh-Warrington, Marnie. *Fifty Key Thinkers on History*. 2nd ed., Abingdon: Routledge, 2007.
6. Khan, Rafiullah and Ifqut Shaheen. Ahmad Hasan Dani's popularization of history/archaeology: its praxes, context and outcomes, *Journal of Asian Civilizations*, 38(1), 2015, 107–130.
7. Khan, Rafiullah and Ifqut Shaheen. Rescuing from Oblivion: Ahmad Hasan Dani and Study of the Indus Civilization, *Ancient Pakistan*, Vol. XXVIII, 2017, 151–162.
8. McAnany, Patricia A. (eds.) *Questioning Collapse: Human Resilience, Ecological Vulnerability and the Aftermath of Empire*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2009.
9. Olivieri, L. M. (2009) Ahmad Hasan Dani: 1920-2009, *East and West*, 59 (1-4), 379–384.
10. Qadir, Asghar. *History of Science in Central Asia: Proceedings of the National Seminar on the History of Science in Central Asian Civilizations*. Islamabad: Quaid-i-Azam University, Islamabad, 1978.
11. Shaheen, Ifqut. Civilizational Ideal. *The News of Sunday*, January 22, 2017, <https://www.thenews.com.pk/tns/detail/562546-civilisational-ideal>.
12. Shaheen, I. (2022). Gandhara in Pakistani Imagination: Ahmad Hasan Dani's View. *Annals of Human and Social Sciences*, 3(3), 294–298. [https://doi.org/10.35484/ahss.2022\(3-III\)28](https://doi.org/10.35484/ahss.2022(3-III)28).
13. Trigger, Bruce. *Understanding Early Civilizations: A Comparative Study*. New York: Cambridge University Press, 2003.